

Investigation on Criticality and Burnup Performance of Pebble Bed Reactor with Thorium-based Nuclear Fuel

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Thorium-based nuclear fuel has become an interesting subject for a variety of research with a wide range of applications. Research focusing on thorium-based fuel is aimed to overcome the scarcity and limitation of natural uranium resources as an alternative nuclear fuel in a thermal reactor. As thorium has no naturally occurring fissile isotope, it requires other fissile isotopes in order to be converted into fissile ^{233}U to produce energy. The isotopes ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu are two of the few alternatives available as the fissile nuclei for a thorium-fueled reactor. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the criticality and burnup performance of pebble bed reactor using two options of thorium-based fuel—namely, $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ and $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$. The HTR-10 was chosen as the reactor model. A series of criticality calculations with various uranium contents in $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel and various plutonium contents in $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel was conducted using the Monte Carlo transport code MCNP6 and continuous energy nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII. The calculation result shows that 35% plutonium content in $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel has comparable criticality with 80% uranium content in $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel. The former is shown to be better to ensure longer reactor operational time. However, that is due to the higher fissile fraction compared to that of the latter fuel. Meanwhile, thorium played little part in prolonging reactor criticality, as ^{233}U production is not particularly significant.

Keywords: burnup, criticality, ENDF/B-VII, MCNP6, pebble bed reactor, thorium-based nuclear fuel

INTRODUCTION

Thorium-based nuclear fuel has become an interesting subject for a variety of research with a wide range of applications. Research focusing on thorium-based fuel is aimed to overcome the scarcity and limitation of natural uranium resources as an alternative nuclear fuel in a thermal reactor. Thorium abundance in the Earth's crust is estimated to be three to four times higher than uranium. The chemical form of thorium used as nuclear

fuel is thorium dioxide (ThO_2), similar to uranium dioxide (UO_2). Compared to UO_2 , however, ThO_2 fuel has superior dimensional stability, higher thermal conductivity, and lower thermal expansion. ThO_2 fuel has a very high melting point of $3,300^\circ\text{C}$, thus giving higher thermal stability than UO_2 , which melts at $2,850^\circ\text{C}$. These material properties are beneficial for its use as a fuel in high-temperature gas-cooled reactor with high burnup and very high temperature (Gintner 2010; Mulder 2009).

Thorium naturally has only one isotope: ^{232}Th . Since it is a fertile isotope, it cannot be directly used in a nuclear

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reactor to induce chain fission reaction. Thorium requires fissile isotopes to be converted into ^{233}U to produce energy. A practical way often used to introduce fissile isotopes is by mixing them with thorium. The isotopes ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu are two of the few alternatives available as the fissile nuclei. ^{235}U is obtained from natural uranium, which has to be enriched for it to be able to maintain chain reaction whilst providing excess neutron to convert ^{232}Th into ^{233}U . Unlike ^{235}U , plutonium does not occur naturally. However, spent nuclear fuel contains plutonium and is recoverable to provide a fissile isotope for thorium. ^{239}Pu isotope is formed from one neutron capture in ^{238}U . Subsequent neutron capture, if not fissioned, forms higher plutonium isotopes – typically ^{240}Pu , ^{241}Pu , and ^{242}Pu .

The feasibility of thorium utilization has been demonstrated in several types of reactors such as the PWR (pressurized water reactor) Indian Point Reactor with a $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ core (93% enriched ^{235}U) and maximum burnup of 32 MWD/kg HM. The PWR Shippingport adopted ThO_2 and (U, Th) fuel rods with a seed-and-blanket concept operated as light water breeder reactors with burnup of 60 MWD/kg HM. The high density $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel was applied in the BWRs (boiling water reactors) Borax IV and Elk River reactors, HTGRs (high-temperature gas-cooled reactors) *Arbeitsgemeinschaft Versuchsreaktor* and thorium high-temperature reactor (THTR), and fast breeder test reactor in India while the $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel has been employed in Lingen, Germany for an experiment of fuel test (Maiorino *et al.* 2017; IAEA 2007).

A series of studies have been performed to assess the potential of thorium utilization in HTGRs. The utilization of thorium fuel mixed with plutonium or minor actinides has been analyzed in a pebble bed modular reactor (PBMR-400) (Acir and Coşkun 2012). This study aims to reduce the accumulation of plutonium and minor actinides in nuclear waste generated by the operation of nuclear power plants (NPPs) over several decades. The possibility of utilizing thorium with weapon-grade plutonium (WGrPu) has been investigated in a gas turbine–modular helium reactor (GT-MHR) (Şahin *et al.* 2012; Şahin and Erol 2012). In this research, the performance of the original and WGrPu fuels in a GT-MHR type reactor was examined through calculations using the MCNP5 code with ENDF/B-VI, Monteburns-2.0, and Origen-2.2 libraries. The GT-MHR reactor geometry was also used as a model reactor to study reactor-grade plutonium fuel in mixed forms with the fertile fuels ^{232}Th and ^{238}U (Şahin *et al.* 2016).

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the criticality and burnup performance of pebble bed reactor with two compositions of thorium-based fuels – namely, $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ and $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$. The HTR-10 (Wu *et al.* 2002) was chosen as reactor model due to the sufficiently

complete availability of design parameters – including core specifications, material characteristics, and other relevant information that can be utilized for studies with a desired computational model. A series of criticality calculations with various uranium contents in $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel and various plutonium contents in $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel was conducted using the Monte Carlo transport code MCNP6 (Goorley *et al.* 2013) and the continuous energy nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII (Chadwick *et al.* 2006). CINDER90 depletion module (Wilson *et al.* 2006) integrated into MCNP6 was utilized in estimating the fuel burnup and completing the analysis of burnup inter-comparison between HTR-10 cores using thorium-based fuel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

HTR-10 Reactor

HTR-10 design is used as the reference design in this study. It is a pebble bed reactor cooled by helium gas and moderated by graphite with thermal power of 10 MW. The general reactor design parameter is given in Table 1. The basic geometry of HTR-10 consists of a cylindrical core with a diameter of 180 cm and an effective height of 197 cm. The active core with a nominal volume of 5 m³ contains approximately 27,000 spherical pebbles with a composition of 57% fuel pebbles and 43% moderator pebbles and a packing fraction of 0.61. The moderator pebbles made of pure graphite are first dropped randomly at the lower part of the core with the same packing of 0.61. The fuel pebbles are continuously recirculated downward through the core five times using a multi-pass

Table 1. The reactor design parameter of HTR-10 (Wu *et al.* 2002).

Reactor parameter	
Thermal power (MW)	10
Inlet/outlet helium temperature (°C)	250/700
Helium pressure (MPa)	3
Helium mass flowrate at full power (kg/s)	4.3
Number of control rods	10
Number of small absorber balls	7
Core specification	
Core diameter/height (cm)	180/197
Average core power density (MW/m ³)	2
Number of pebbles in full load	27,000
Packing fraction of pebble	0.61
Average discharge burnup (MWd/t)	80,000
Fuel cycle scheme	Multi-pass

scheme until reaching the design burnup of 80 GWd/t. This on-line refueling, which allows fuel pebble to be removed or added during reactor operation, cannot be modeled using MCNP6 code; therefore, a static pebble bed was used.

To investigate the effect of thorium-based nuclear fuel, in this work, the TRISO particle comprises a spherical fuel kernel of $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ with 17% enriched ^{235}U . Another TRISO particle comprises a spherical fuel kernel of $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ with plutonium isotopic vector produced from the irradiation of 3.7% enriched UO_2 fuel in PWR with a burnup of 41.2 GWd/t and cooling time of 3 yr. The two kernels are coated by four protective coating layers of porous carbon buffer (C), inner pyrolytic carbon (iPyC), silicon carbide (SiC), and outer pyrolytic carbon (oPyC). The thicknesses of each layer are 0.009, 0.004, 0.0035, and 0.004 cm, respectively. The coating layers act as multiple defenses and barriers for fission product retention and maintain the integrity of the TRISO particle under a temperature limit of 1600 °C. The fuel pebble is composed of 8,335 TRISO particles. Its schematic view of the fuel pebble is shown in Figure 1. The uranium content in $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel and plutonium content in $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel was varied from 1–100% to analyze the criticality and burnup performance of these fuels in the pebble bed reactor. The specifications of fuel and moderator pebbles are given in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The isotopic plutonium vector is given in Table 4.

Table 2. Specification of fuel pebble.

Fuel pebble		
Fuel composition 1	$\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$	
Fuel composition 2	$\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$	
Fuel pebble radius (cm)	3	
Fueled zone radius (cm)	2.5	
Graphite density in matrix/shell (g/cm^3)	1.73	
Natural boron impurity in fuel/graphite (ppm)	1.0/1.3	
TRISO coated particle		
Material	Density (g/cm^3)	Outer radius (cm)
Kernel	10.40	0.0250
Buffer	1.10	0.0340
iPyC	1.90	0.0380
SiC	3.18	0.0415
oPyC	1.90	0.0455

Table 3. Specification of moderator pebble (Jing and Sun 1998).

Moderator pebble radius (cm)	3
Graphite density in moderator pebble (g/cm^3)	1.84
Natural boron impurity in graphite (ppm)	1.30

Figure 1. The schematic view of fuel pebble (Setiadipura *et al.* 2015).

Table 4. Plutonium isotopic vector.

Isotope	Pu concentration (%)
^{238}Pu	2.59
^{239}Pu	53.85
^{240}Pu	23.66
^{241}Pu	13.13
^{242}Pu	6.77

Calculation Model

The calculation of the pebble bed reactor is inseparable from the double heterogeneity problem consisting of TRISO coated particles in fuel pebble and a combination of fuel and moderator pebbles in the reactor core. The MCNP6 code has superior capability in modeling the extra-complex geometry of the reactor. In this work, the modeling of HTR-10 consists of the pebbles and the core models. These models play an important role before performing the neutronic calculations such as criticality, reactivity, neutron spectrum and flux, spatial distribution of power and temperature, depletion and burnup of fuel, kinetic parameters, *etc.*

Pebble model. The model was constructed by defining the body-centered cubic (BCC) lattice of fuel and moderator pebbles. One fuel pebble was placed at the center of the lattice and eight of 1/8 moderator pebbles were positioned at the corners of the lattice. Helium coolant occupies the empty region outside the pebbles in the lattice. The radius of the moderator pebble was reduced from 3 to 2.7310 cm to preserve the composition of 57% fuel pebbles and 43% moderator pebbles in the reactor core. The pitch of the BCC lattice was then adjusted from 7.1853 to 6.8772 cm to reproduce a pebble packing fraction of 0.61.

The TRISO particle was modeled with a simple cubic (SC) lattice. The kernel with its four coating layers was located at the center of the lattice and the rest region outside the TRISO particle was occupied by graphite matrix. The fuel pebble was created by filling coated fuel particles in SC lattice into the fueled zone with a repetitive structure feature of MCNP6. The cubic lattice pitch of 0.1988 cm was calculated from the relationship between the radius of the fueled zone and the number of TRISO particles per pebble. The TRISO packing fraction of 5.0248% was obtained from this pitch value. The MCNP6 model for SC lattice of TRISO particle and BCC lattice of fuel and moderator pebbles are illustrated in Figures 2 and 3, respectively.

The isotopic concentration of TRISO coated particles is given in Table 5. In this table, the fuel kernel of $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ has 70% uranium content and $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ has 30% plutonium content. The isotopic concentration of graphite matrix and graphite shell, which is identical, is given in Table 6.

Figure 2. SC lattice of TRISO particle.

Figure 3. BCC lattice of fuel and moderator pebbles.

Table 5. Isotopic concentration of TRISO particle (atom/barn-cm).

Kernel $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$			
^{235}U	2.79209×10^{-3}	O	4.67639×10^{-2}
^{238}U	1.34598×10^{-2}	^{10}B	1.14694×10^{-7}
^{232}Th	7.13009×10^{-3}	^{11}B	4.64570×10^{-7}
Kernel $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$			
^{238}Pu	1.79862×10^{-4}	^{232}Th	1.66236×10^{-2}
^{239}Pu	3.72391×10^{-3}	O	4.70390×10^{-2}
^{240}Pu	1.62934×10^{-3}	^{10}B	1.14694×10^{-7}
^{241}Pu	9.00434×10^{-4}	^{11}B	4.64570×10^{-7}
^{232}Pu	4.62354×10^{-4}		
Coating layers			
	Buffer		SiC
C	5.51513×10^{-2}	^{28}Si	4.40195×10^{-2}
	iPyC/oPyC	^{29}Si	2.24945×10^{-3}
C	9.52614×10^{-2}	^{30}Si	1.49008×10^{-3}
		C	4.77590×10^{-2}

Table 6. Isotopic concentration of graphite matrix and graphite shell (atom/barn-cm) (Jing and Sun 1998).

Graphite matrix		Graphite shell	
C	8.674169×10^{-2}	C	8.674169×10^{-2}
^{10}B	2.244010×10^{-8}	^{10}B	2.244010×10^{-8}
^{11}B	9.032424×10^{-8}	^{11}B	9.032424×10^{-8}

Core model. The core model was constructed by filling fuel and moderator pebbles in BCC lattice into the reactor core with a repetitive structure feature of MCNP6. The extra pebbles in the core contributed by clipped fuel pebble and clipped moderator pebble on the core wall due to the use of repetitive structure were compensated by applying an exclusive zone of helium surrounding the core with a thickness of 1.71 cm. The emergence of clipped TRISO particles on the surface wall of the fueled zone was not corrected because its small packing fraction would not have a significant effect on the calculation results. The cone at the bottom of the core was modeled by filling moderator pebbles in BCC lattice with helium in the empty gap between the pebbles.

The surface descriptions provided in the MCNP6 were utilized in the pebbles and core models. Cells formed by surface cards in the input data were defined as UNIVERSE. The FILL and LATTICE options were applied on a set of UNIVERSE to describe the fuel pebble and reactor core geometry with great detail according to its actual description. Other reactor components such as helium flow channels, irradiation experiment channels, and also shutdown system channels consisting of control rods and small absorber balls in the graphite reflector side were thoroughly modeled. The vertical and horizontal views of the MCNP6 model for core calculation are illustrated in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. The modeling procedure in this study was first introduced at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (Lebenhaft 2001) and was used as a reference for calculation model in some

Figure 4. Vertical view of MCNP6 model for core calculation.

Figure 5. Horizontal view of MCNP6 model for core calculation.

publications (Alzamly *et al.* 2020; Zuhair *et al.* 2017, 2020; Zuhair *et al.* 2019a, b; Hosseini and Athari-Allaf 2012, 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the MCNP6 calculation, KCODE and KSRC cards as two important standard features should be used to quantify the criticality and other reactor parameters. In the KCODE card, 10,000 neutron histories per cycle with a total of 250 active cycles were simulated for the convergence of fission source distribution. The 50 initial cycles were skipped prior to the beginning of the tallies so that the contamination of the results by the initial source guess was negligible. The total number of neutron histories resulted in a k-value with a standard deviation of less than 64 pcm. The initial spatial distribution of fission neutrons was entered by using the KSRC card and was located in the center of the reactor. The thermal scattering library $S(\alpha, \beta)$ was used to consider the molecular binding effect affecting the thermal neutron interactions with all materials containing graphite in the energy region below ~ 4 eV. The outer boundary of the HTR-10 reactor system was assumed as a vacuum condition so that the neutron current was zero. The temperature was set at 900 K and all control rods were fully withdrawn.

HTR-10 criticality calculation result with $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel for infinite (k_{inf}) and finite (k_{eff}) reactor dimensions are illustrated in Figure 6. It is observed from the figure that the reactor becomes critical at $\pm 70\%$ uranium content. Beyond 70%, the criticality increases less drastically with increasing uranium content. At 80% uranium content, the reactor is able to run with a typical k_{eff} of 1.04642 ± 0.00055 . The higher the uranium content, the longer the fuel lifetime inside the reactor will become. In a thermal reactor like HTR-10, significantly higher uranium content

Figure 6. Criticality with $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel.

is needed in fuel to compensate ^{232}Th , which has a higher thermal absorption cross-section.

The growing accumulation of plutonium resulted from an NPP and military activities raises serious public and political concerns in the world about the radiotoxicity dangers and misuse of plutonium for purpose of making nuclear weapons. One alternative for reducing the amounts of plutonium and the stockpiles of military plutonium as much as possible is to burn them in the reactors as fuel. However, plutonium core is not particularly advisable because its performance tends to result in transient behavior, which can lead to a fatal accident situation. Therefore, mixing plutonium with thorium fuel is recommended to breed additional nuclear fuel *in situ*.

The HTR-10 criticality calculation result with $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel for infinite (k_{inf}) and finite (k_{eff}) reactor dimensions is illustrated in Figure 7. The figure shows that the reactor becomes critical at $\sim 20\%$ plutonium content. Similar to the $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel, beyond 30% , the criticality increases comparatively small with increasing plutonium content. At 35% plutonium content, the reactor is critical with k_{eff} of 1.05298 ± 0.00063 . As plutonium recovered from light-water reactor spent fuel does not have a fissile content restriction like enriched uranium, the required plutonium content in order to have comparable criticality is understandably lower. It allows higher thorium fraction in plutonium core and, conversely, severely limits thorium loading in uranium core. Moreover, in general, plutonium-based fuel has a larger number of average neutrons produced per fission compared to the ^{235}U fuel. More importantly, the ^{235}U fissile is slightly better than that of ^{239}Pu for the thermal energy region; however, for intermediate and fast energy regions, the reproduction factor (η) value indicates that the neutrons produced from fission per absorption in

Figure 7. Criticality with $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel.

fuel isotope for ^{239}Pu are superior than that of ^{235}U . The η value also tends to be higher in intermediate and fast energy regions compared to that of the thermal energy region. Considering these η value characteristics, it is clear that the higher contribution of intermediate and fast energy regions to the total fission in the $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ system gives a significant contribution to the better criticality in the $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ system compared to that of the $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ system. With a 35% content, the plutonium-based fuel has reached good condition for operational compared to 80% for ^{235}U based fuel. With ThO_2 content of about 65% compared to 20% for that in ^{235}U based fuel, plutonium-based fuel has a better ^{233}U supply in the middle and the end of life.

The calculation result of changes in criticality with $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ and $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuels for infinite (k_{inf}) reactor dimension as a function of operation time is illustrated in Figure 8. The initial value of k_{inf} for $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel (1.70698 ± 0.00040) is exceedingly high and far higher than that of $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ (1.38728 ± 0.00057) fuel, but it decreases sharply and reaches the value of 1.1 at operation time of about 900 d. The k_{inf} value above 1.1 is considered as the limit where the reactor will reach criticality by taking into account neutron leakage. The $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel decreases slowly and reaches operational time for 1800 d or twice that of $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel. This means that, from a viewpoint of the neutron economy, the use of $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel is more effective and would enable a long reactor operation time. In this condition, plutonium content in $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel is 35% and uranium content in $\text{UO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel is 80% .

Change in fuel concentration due to burnup is another important aspect of reactor design. Figures 9, 10, and 11

Figure 8. K_{inf} of UO_2 - ThO_2 and PuO_2 - ThO_2 fuels against operational time.

Figure 11. Concentration of ^{233}U in UO_2 - ThO_2 and PuO_2 - ThO_2 fuels.

Figure 9. Concentration of ^{232}Th in UO_2 - ThO_2 and PuO_2 - ThO_2 fuels.

Figure 10. Concentration of ^{233}Pa in UO_2 - ThO_2 and PuO_2 - ThO_2 fuels.

illustrate the concentration change of ^{232}Th , ^{233}Pa , and ^{233}U . Figure 9 shows that ^{232}Th concentration change in both fuel options tends to be similar. Nonetheless, ^{232}Th concentration in UO_2 - ThO_2 fuel decreases faster since ^{232}Th have a larger capture cross-section than ^{238}U , despite the latter having the higher concentration and is, thus, more likely to capture neutron. Concurrently, ^{232}Th is the only fertile fuel in the PuO_2 - ThO_2 option. Consequently, there was no such “competition” and, thus, ^{232}Th concentration appears to decrease more slowly. Another factor is the effectiveness of ^{233}U , converted from ^{232}Th , as nuclear fuel compared to ^{239}Pu in the thermal spectrum, which needs less fertile conversion.

Figure 10 illustrates the change of ^{233}Pa concentration along the operational time. A sharp increase of ^{233}Pa is observed in PuO_2 - ThO_2 fuel during the first 10 days of operation before its accumulation slows down and increases in an exponential pattern thereafter. A similar pattern is observed in UO_2 - ThO_2 fuel but initially in a lower concentration due to smaller ^{232}Th content. However, ^{233}Pa increase in the latter option is steeper. In Day 900, its ^{233}Pa concentration overtook PuO_2 - ThO_2 before peaking on Day 1300. A possible explanation is that ^{233}U is generated enough to induce more neutron capture of ^{232}Th , which led to more ^{233}Pa formation, judging from the apparent higher ^{232}Th decrease rate after Day 900.

Meanwhile, in PuO_2 - ThO_2 fuel, larger ^{233}U build-up due to ^{232}Th sole fertile fuel existence means that ^{233}Pa is the only fissile precursor that exists. Due to its medium (27.2 d) half-life and relatively large capture cross-section, a certain amount of ^{233}Pa nuclide was converted into practically useless ^{234}U , thereby reducing the ^{233}Pa accumulation rate compared to UO_2 - ThO_2 fuel. This ^{233}Pa

characteristic potentially reduces the neutron economy of the PuO₂-ThO₂ system. To optimize the neutron economy on this fuel option, fuel recirculation time must be reconsidered to allow ²³³Pa to decay into ²³³U instead of absorbing a neutron.

Figure 11 describes ²³³U concentration change. Fissile isotope ²³³U is formed from thorium by neutron capture followed by two successive beta decays. PuO₂-ThO₂ fuel showed a more drastic increase of ²³³U concentration, thanks to its large ²³²Th concentration. ²³³U accumulation peaked on Day 1700. It is when the remaining fissile Pu is no longer sufficient to help sustain a chain reaction and fission products are accumulated large enough, after which ²³³U concentration started to decrease.

UO₂-ThO₂ fuel, on the other hand, understandably showed less increase due to the existence of ²³⁸U, which is converted into less desirable ²³⁹Pu. The latter performs worst in thermal reactors since fewer neutrons are generated to sustain a chain reaction and breed fissile fuel. Thus, its formation worsens the neutron economy of a ²³⁸U-rich fuel. This combination led to ²³³U consumed much earlier than the PuO₂-ThO₂ option, peaking in Day 900 before decreasing. The lack of ²³³U generation also explains the rapid decrease of UO₂-ThO₂ *k*_{inf} value despite its initial *k*_{inf} being higher than that of the other option.

CONCLUSION

Investigation on criticality and burnup performance of pebble bed reactor with thorium-based nuclear fuel has been performed using a series calculation with MCNP6 code and ENDF/B-VII library. The calculation result shows that a 35% plutonium content in PuO₂-ThO₂ fuel has comparable criticality with 80% uranium content in UO₂-ThO₂ fuel. ²³²Th concentration decreases faster in UO₂-ThO₂ fuel. In short, the PuO₂-ThO₂ option is shown to be better in terms of fuel utilization. However, it is merely due to the fact that Pu concentration is higher at the beginning of life, while ²³³U converted from ²³²Th is not particularly significant in extending fuel cycle length. Inherent safety and kinetic parameters of the fuels should be evaluated in future works, as well as the fuel recirculation period, in order to optimize the neutron economy.

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